

Socialism, Green Socialism: Evaluating the Impact of Urban Morphology on Microclimate Regulation

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Abstract: This study analyses surface thermal patterns across five residential neighbourhoods in Zagreb, Croatia, using multi-temporal Landsat 8/9 thermal infrared imagery to retrieve Land Surface Temperature (LST). Transect-based thermal profiling examines how urban form and the configuration of urban green infrastructure influence micro-scale thermal behaviour during peak summer conditions. Results show a consistent divergence in LST linked to construction era, planning scale, and surface permeability. Socialist-era neighbourhoods, planned at district or neighbourhood scale with integrated green space, systematically record lower temperatures than post-socialist infill, developed at finer planning granularities with reduced permeability. The spatial continuity of urban green infrastructure (UGI), rather than total green coverage, emerges as the decisive cooling factor, with district-scale parks functioning as thermal anchors well beyond their immediate boundaries. These findings provide a data-driven basis for climate-responsive retrofitting of Zagreb's residential zones.

Keywords: urban heat island; urban morphology; urban green infrastructure.

1 Introduction

Rapid global urbanisation has transformed natural landscapes into dense, impervious urban fabrics, intensifying the Urban Heat Island (UHI) effect (Radhi et al. 2013). Characterised by elevated temperatures in urban areas relative to their rural surroundings, UHI poses significant challenges to public health, energy demand, and climate resilience. As heatwaves become more frequent and severe, Urban Green Infrastructure (UGI) has shifted from an aesthetic amenity to a critical component of climate-responsive urban planning (Lopes et al. 2025).

Zagreb, Croatia's capital, provides a valuable context for examining these dynamics. Its residential fabric reflects a pronounced contrast between the large-scale, planned housing estates of the socialist period (1945–1990) and the denser, market-driven developments of the post-socialist era (Ivanković 2024). Socialist planning typically prioritised human-centred design, incorporating extensive and interconnected green spaces (Tandarić et al. 2025). In contrast, recent “investor urbanism” has often resulted in increased building density, reduced per-capita greenery, and more fragmented open spaces—conditions that may intensify localised thermal (Zlatař 2014).

Although the cooling effects of vegetation are well established, commonly using indices such as the Normalised Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), such approaches often rely on static spatial averages that

overlook microclimatic variability. Advances in thermal remote sensing, particularly through Landsat 8 and 9 Thermal Infrared Sensor (TIRS) data, enable more detailed estimation of Land Surface Temperature (LST) (Khalil and Kumar 2025). However, mapping thermal hotspots alone is insufficient, translating these insights into urban design strategies requires linking satellite-derived data with the spatial and morphological characteristics of the built environment (Liu et al. 2023).

This study addresses this gap by analysing thermal profiles across distinct residential typologies in Zagreb. We employ transect-based thermal profiling to examine how the configuration—not merely the quantity—of green infrastructure interacts with building form and construction period. The paper further compares how socialist-era planning and contemporary infill development influence the city's thermal performance during peak summer conditions.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Study area

The study focuses on Zagreb, selected for its diverse residential morphology. Five neighbourhoods were chosen to represent a range of construction periods and housing typologies, primarily multi-family developments with some single-family housing areas included for comparison. Thermal transects were defined in neighbourhoods of Vrbani, Špansko, Središće–Zaprude, Trokut–Trnsko–Siget, and Dugave–Hrelić. As shown in Figure 1, these transects capture variations in urban form, including differences in density, building typology, and greenspace distribution, enabling comparison of their influence on local thermal conditions.

Together, the five transects span a temporal and morphological spectrum from socialist-era modernist urban planning to contemporary market-driven infill, capturing variation in building density, greenspace distribution, and planning scale across the city's residential fabric (Figure 1).

2.2 Methodology

To assess urban thermal patterns, this study combines meteorological data analysis with thermal remote sensing. Maximum air temperatures recorded during the summer months over the past five years were obtained from the Maksimir weather station. Based on these records, three cloud-free satellite images per year were selected, corresponding to peak heat conditions (Table 1).

Figure 1. Study area, locations of the thermal transects and LST-based UHI intensity map.

Thermal data were derived from Landsat 8 and Landsat 9, specifically using their TIRS bands (L2C2 dataset). These sensors provide thermal measurements at a native resolution of 100 m, resampled to 30 m. Standard preprocessing steps were applied to convert digital numbers to at-sensor radiance, followed by brightness temperature and LST retrieval. The analysis and retrieval of thermal data was done using ArcPro software.

A composite mean LST map was generated from the selected images to represent UHI intensity under extreme summer conditions. This approach minimises temporal anomalies and highlights persistent spatial patterns of surface heating. Subsequently, LST values were extracted along the predefined thermal transects described in the previous section, allowing for a continuous, profile-based analysis of temperature variation across different urban morphologies.

Table 1. Dates of selected cloud-free Landsat 8 and Landsat 9 scenes corresponding to peak summer conditions, used for LST estimation.

Year	Image 1	Image 2	Image 3
2021	17/06/2021	24/08/2021	12/09/2021
2022	27/06/2022	22/07/2022	20/08/2022
2023	09/07/2023	17/07/2023	26/08/2023
2024	11/07/2024	27/07/2024	14/08/2024
2025	06/07/2025	14/07/2025	14/08/2025

3 Results

Figure 2 illustrates the spatial variation of LST along the defined transects, expressed as distance (m) from the origin point shown in Figure 1. Across all transects, LST ranges from approximately 37 to 46 °C, with higher temperatures consistently associated with post-socialist, high-density development and lower permeability, while socialist-era neighbourhood-scale planning and green spaces correspond to cooler conditions.

Figure 2. Thermal transect showing LST variation along the established axes.

The Središće–Zaprude axis shows the widest thermal range (38–46 °C) (Figure 2-A). The densified SW Središće segment, developed in the 2010s with low permeability, records the highest temperatures (43–46 °C), whereas the planned 1960s neighbourhood of Zaprude remains substantially cooler (38–40 °C). Vjekoslav Majer Park (buffer zone between Središće and Zaprude) and adjacent undeveloped land act as distinct cooling zones.

The Dugave–Hrelič axis highlights the contrast between planned and unplanned urban fabric (Figure 2-B). Dugave, a low-density socialist-era neighbourhood with high permeability, records some of the lowest residential temperatures (38–40 °C), while the dense and weakly planned Hrelič area reaches 41–44 °C.

The Špansko axis demonstrates the thermal impact of contemporary infill development (Figure 2-C). The older Špansko neighbourhood maintains moderate temperatures (40–43 °C), whereas the high-density GIK infill (new Špansko) reaches 44–45 °C. The nearby Pionir development (end of the transect) records slightly lower values (41–43 °C), indicating that greater surface permeability can partly mitigate heat accumulation.

The Trokut–Trnsko–Siget axis further confirms the cooling role of planned green space (Figure 2-D). Trnsko and Siget generally remain within 38–42 °C, with the lowest values occurring near Newlyweds Park and greener sections of Siget. In contrast, the unplanned and dense Trokut settlement reaches 42–44 °C.

Finally, the Vrbani axis illustrates how successive densification phases increase thermal intensity within the same area (Figure 2-E). Temperatures rise from 41–43 °C in the permeable, low-density Vrbani I to 44–45 °C in the denser and less permeable Vrbani II, while Vrbani III shows intermediate values (42–44 °C).

4 Discussion

The results consistently show that higher thermal intensity is associated with post-socialist, market-driven development, while lower temperatures characterise socialist-era neighbourhoods. However, the evidence suggests that this contrast is not primarily a function of construction era per se, but rather of the planning philosophy each era embodied. Dugave and Zapruđe perform well thermally not simply because they are older, but because they were designed at neighbourhood scale with integrated, spatially continuous greenspace. In contrast, unplanned neighbourhoods consisting of densely built family houses (e.g., Trokut, Hreljić) record temperatures comparable to those of post-socialist infill. This finding nuances a simplistic “socialist = cool” reading and redirects attention to the structural conditions that socialist planning enabled rather than to the era itself.

Across all five axes, planning scale emerges as a key mediating variable. The planning scale is often related to surface permeability. Post-socialist planning generally shifted from neighbourhood to section and even land-parcel scale, focusing on providing housing without much consideration of the quality of the urban environment, which is often reflected in the lack of permeable surfaces. Segments planned at the district or neighbourhood scale consistently record lower LST than those developed at the section, parcel, or cul-de-sac scale, even when the building typology is similar. This pattern implies that the problem driving thermal intensification in post-socialist Zagreb is not density per se, but the spatial unit in which planning decisions are made. The Vrbani and Špansko axes illustrate this trajectory in compact form. Each development phase that reduced planning scale and surface permeability produced a measurable increase in LST, mirroring the broader pattern of “investor urbanism” across the city (Zlataar 2014). This aligns with Liu et al. (2023), who found that urban morphology at the neighbourhood scale is a stronger predictor of UHI intensity than individual building characteristics.

The role of permeable surfaces and UGI configuration is equally clear. Parks such as Newlyweds Park (distance 1000–1250 m, transect D) and Vjekoslav Majer Park (distance 800m and 2500m, transect A) produce cooling effects along the transects, demonstrating that spatially connected green infrastructure exerts influence beyond its immediate footprint. Furthermore, neighbourhoods

planned with buildings and roads nested in the greenspace matrix (e.g. Zapruđe, Dugave, Trnsko) show lower LST compared to neighbourhoods with patchy greenspaces (e.g. Vrbani II and III, Špansko–Oranice) and especially compared to high-density areas with low permeability and highly fragmented or absent greenery, which sustain thermal peaks regardless of other morphological characteristics. This supports the argument, advanced by Lopes et al. (2025) and others, that UGI connectivity and spatial continuity matter more than total green coverage. The Pionir buildings on the Špansko axis offer a partial counterexample: medium permeability appears to partially offset high density, suggesting that surface treatment can meaningfully moderate thermal intensity even in the absence of large green patches.

Several limitations should be acknowledged. First, Landsat-derived LST represents surface temperatures of roofs, pavements, and vegetation canopies rather than street-level air temperature or human thermal comfort conditions. As such, LST should not be interpreted as a direct measure of pedestrian heat exposure, particularly because it does not capture vertical surfaces, shading dynamics, or microclimatic conditions within street canyons. Nevertheless, LST remains valuable for identifying the spatial structure and intensity of urban heat patterns at the neighbourhood scale, providing continuous spatial coverage that is difficult to achieve using in-situ measurements alone. Second, the 30 m spatial resolution of Landsat likely underestimates fine-scale thermal variability and peak temperatures at the building level, while the composite LST approach does not capture short-duration heat events. Finally, morphological variables were characterised qualitatively, limiting statistical generalisation. Future research should combine remotely sensed LST with in-situ or modelled air temperature data, incorporate quantitative morphological indicators, and include field-based validation to better link urban form, surface heating, and human thermal exposure.

The practical implications are clear. Retrofitting high-density post-socialist infill should prioritise permeable surface treatments and the creation of connected green corridors over isolated tree planting, which the data suggest has limited thermal impact. Socialist-era neighbourhoods with intact, neighbourhood-scale green networks offer a replicable spatial template for climate-responsive planning — not as a model to be replicated uncritically, but as evidence that integrated greenspace planning at the right scale produces measurable and durable thermal benefits.

5 Conclusions

This study identifies consistent spatial differences in LST across residential neighbourhoods in Zagreb that correspond to variations in construction period, planning scale, building density, and surface permeability. Neighbourhoods developed during the socialist period generally exhibit lower surface temperatures than more recent high-density infill developments, while areas with greater continuity of green and permeable surfaces tend to

display cooler thermal patterns. Although these relationships were identified through comparative spatial analysis rather than quantified statistical modelling, the results indicate that urban form and land-cover structure are closely associated with neighbourhood-scale thermal conditions.

The findings contribute to ongoing discussions on climate-responsive urban planning in post-socialist cities undergoing densification. By mapping spatial thermal contrasts across different urban morphologies, the study provides a basis for identifying areas potentially vulnerable to heat accumulation and for supporting planning decisions related to green infrastructure, permeability, and development intensity. Future research combining higher-resolution data, quantitative morphological metrics, and air-temperature measurements could further strengthen the applicability of these findings for urban climate adaptation and public-health planning.

6 References

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